

SoildiverAgro project

Adoption of new management practices to increase crop production and quality

THE WHAT AND WHY

Combined Use of Biostimulant, Adjuvant, and Reduced Fungicides in Wheat Cultivation in Germany

This case study looks at how using a plant biostimulant and a plant adjuvant, along with reduced amounts of fungicides, affects conventional wheat farming in North Western Germany. The two products are expected to help roots grow better, improve how plants take in water and nutrients, and support soil health and biodiversity. The goal of the study is to see if these practices can strengthen the soil's natural processes and help reduce fungal diseases like Fusarium by supporting helpful soil organisms that feed on fungi.

In the second year of the experiment (2022), three different treatments were used:

- The first treatment (T1) was a control and involved normal wheat farming with reduced fungicide use.
- The second treatment (T2) used the additive Kantor and

the biostimulant Nutri Phite Magnum S, along with reduced fungicides.

- The third treatment (T3) included everything from T2 and also added a plant adjuvant called Smart Seed G.

In all treatments, the spacing between the seed rows was 22.5 cm due to technical reasons. Other farming activities like fertilization and soil preparation were the same across all treatments. During the growing seasons of 2021 and 2023, when potatoes and barley were grown, all plots followed the usual local farming practices.

Table

The table below shows how gross margins vary according to the different agricultural practices used.

	Costs (€/ha)	Revenues (€/ha)	Gross margin (€/ha)
T1: Control	1,898	5,154	3,256
T2: Conventional wheat cultivation + use of additive + plant biostimulant	1,913	4,776	2,863
T3: Conventional wheat cultivation + use of additive + plant biostimulant + plant adjuvant + reduction of fungicides	1,928	4,430	2,502

1. Average value of production costs, sales revenues, and gross margins, calculated for each practice analysed in a 3-year rotation (potato-winter wheat-barley).

KEYWORDS

Economic profitability, gross margin, biostimulant, wheat cultivation, fusarium

AUTHORSHIP

Birte Tschentke, Flächenagentur Rheinland, Germany
David-Alexander Bind, Flächenagentur Rheinland, Germany
Martin Banse, Thünen Institute, Germany
Christine van Capelle, Thünen Institute, Germany

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